

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa)

Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: A geolinguistic approach to linguistic patterns

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Abstract: This study draws linguistic maps of the alignment patterns in Asian and African languages to analyze the distributions of these patterns and examine their historical development, contrasting intransitive and highly transitive constructions with arguments in equal animacy. The maps that are provided here include an overall map, enlarged-view maps, and maps by type as excerpted from the overall map. The overall map imports the maps provided by the contributors to our previous project. The maps by type clarify the geographical distribution of the alignment patterns. These maps provide examples of the diffusion of linguistic patterns; the alignment patterns may show areal tendencies beyond the differences among genetic groups. Considerably, the ergative-absolutive, tripartite, and transitive patterns show distributions that suggest their histories: the ergative-absolutive type exhibits a continuous distribution in Asia, whereas the tripartite and transitive types are distributed across small but overlapping regions relative to the ergative-absolutive. These distributions suggest the diffusion of the ergative-absolutive type and the later development of tripartite and transitive types. The nominative-accusative patterns without verbal person marking also show an areal tendency in East and Southeast Asia.*

Keywords: *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa*; alignment; grammatical relation; linguistic pattern; linguistic area

1. Introduction

This study draws linguistic maps of the alignment patterns found in Asian and African languages to analyze their distributions and examine their historical process. These maps are based on our previous research project, *Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics*, ILCAA Joint Research Project No. jrp000256, conducted at the Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa, Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, from April 2020 to March 2023. We published 21 interpretive maps

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of alignment patterns that were separately drawn by the contributors, each of whom was responsible for a different language group/area in Fukushima et al. eds. (2023) (*Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa Vol. 3*, henceforth LAAA3). Each article in LAAA3 also contains example sentences to precisely show the characteristics of the alignment patterns in each language group. In addition, Shirai (2023) conducted a fundamental analysis of the overall distribution.

Our project reflects the principles of linguistic geography. Linguistic geography, on principle, does not subject the entire system of a given language/dialect (lect) but separately deals with individual linguistic phenomena (Sibata 1969). Therefore, this project deals with the characteristics exhibited by the specifically restricted construction of each lect. Thus, the maps drawn in the project are intended to focus on individual construction across splits in many languages, and maps reflecting other constructions should be separately drawn. We focused on highly transitive constructions featuring arguments in equal animacy, having the following features, as contrasted with intransitive constructions (Shirai 2023: 63):

- The subject and object are equal in the empathy/animacy/person hierarchy: for example, both are in the third person or animals.
- The subject and object are definite, specific, and/or referential.
- The predicate is simple and/or plain in voice and/or mood.
- The predicate is verbal, with high volitionality and/or affectedness.
- The event described by the sentence has already occurred, is finished, or has been completed in the past.
- The information structure and word order are unmarked or most general.

This study differs from the preceding WALS project (Dryer and Haspelmath eds. 2013) in this respect, in addition to the number of points plotted on the maps.

We provide an example of the diffusion of linguistic patterns by illustrating that some alignment patterns are geographically distributed beyond genetic groups. In earlier study on language contact, language structures such as alignment patterns were considered conservative and less likely to diffuse across language groups (e.g., Thomason and Kaufman 1988: 74–75). Later studies, such as those of Ross (2001, 2007), provided counterexamples in which structures or patterns were borrowed without dense lexical borrowing. Matras and Sakel (2007) used the term pattern replication and investigated its mechanism.

This study provides an overall map connecting the previously developed maps in LAAA3 (Fig. 1), along with enlargements that show details of distributions (Figs. 2–4). Consequently, we excerpt feature-specific maps from the overall map (Figs. 5–10). Section 3 discusses what these distributions suggest for language history, and Section 4 draws conclusions.

2. Methods and results

Table 1 illustrates the basic symbols used in the maps. The letters A, S, and P in the header row indicate the subject of a transitive, the sole argument of an intransitive, and the object of a transitive, respectively. In this project, the contributors used these symbols for basic types, being allowed to use modified symbols to express splits. The project provided symbols for types that seemed logically incongruous, as we intended to be exhaustive, but they did not exist. For this reason, these unattested types are shaded, and the symbols are removed from Table 1 below. For details of the classification, please refer to Shirai (2023).

Table 1 Major types and basic symbols (revised version of Table 1 from Shirai 2023)

	Nominal case marking	Verbal person marking	Double marking	No marking
AS P (Nominative-accusative)	l A1	/ A2	\ A3 ^ AX3	– A4
A SP (Ergative-absolutive)	△ B1	▽ B2	▽ B3 ▾ BX3	B4
S1 S2 (Active-inactive or split intransitive)	≡ C1	C2	◇ C3 ◇ CX3	C4
A S P (Tripartite)	∩ D1	□ D2	◇ D3 ◇ DX3	D4
ASP (Neutral)	E1	○ E2	E3 EX3	○ E4
More than three splits	☆ F			
Other types	(Unspecified symbol) G			

Symbols are presented in different colors corresponding to each language group; however, the distinguishable number of colors is limited. Therefore, some distant language groups are given the same color. Table 2 shows the language groups and the colors given on the map.

Table 2 The language groups and colors

Language group	Color	Language group	Color
Ainu	Red	Korean	Light blue
Andamanese and language isolates (South Asia)	Black	Kra-Dai	Navy
Austroasiatic	Green	Kx'a (Kalahari Basin Area)	Light blue
Austronesian	Orange	Mongolic	Green
Caucasian	Light blue	Niger-Congo	Navy
Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Black	Nilo-Saharan	Green
Dravidian	Red	Semitic	Brown
Hmong-Mien	Orange	Sinitic	Red
Indo-Aryan and Nuristani (South Asia)	Navy	Tibeto-Burman	Brown
Iranian	Orange	Tungusic	Orange
Japonic	Green	Turkic	Light blue
Khoe-Kwadi (Kalahari Basin Area)	Brown	Tuu (Kalahari Basin Area)	Orange
		Uralic	Light blue

2.1. Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: all types

The contributors' maps were imported in the form of layers (Fig. 1). The map shows the alignment patterns of 3,254 points in Asia and Africa, plus parts of Oceania (Austronesian languages) and Europe (Indo-Aryan, Turkic, and Uralic languages). The symbols on the map indicate the principles described above (Tables 1 and 2), except some language groups that use symbols other than those listed above, for which a legend is provided below the map. For details of these classifications, please refer to the articles in LAAA3.

Additional Legend:

Austroasiatic

- ◆ A4v
- ◆ A2v

Niger-Congo

- ▤ A2x
- ▥ A2'
- ▧ A2c
- ▨ A2c/x

Austronesian

- ▩ G3-1
- ▧ G3-2
- ▨ G4-1
- ▩ G4-2

Indo-Aryan and Nuristani

- ⬡ GX3

Iranian

- ◐ G3
- ✦ GX3

Nilo-Saharan

- ◆ G1

Fig. 1 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa

The enlarged map shows the distribution of the alignment patterns in areas featuring dense point concentrations in Figs. 2–4, illustrating the distribution in South and Southeast Asia (Fig. 2), Caucasus and Anatolia (Fig. 3), and Central and South Africa (Fig. 4), respectively.

Fig. 2 Enlarged map of alignment patterns: South and Southeast Asia

Fig. 3 Enlarged map of alignment patterns: the Caucasus and Anatolia

Fig. 4 Enlarged map of alignment patterns: Central and South Africa

2.2. Geographical distribution of each type of alignment

The following maps are provided: nominative-accusative (Fig. 5), ergative-absolutive (Fig. 6), active-inactive (Fig. 7), tripartite (Fig. 8), neutral or hierarchical (Fig. 9), and other types (Fig. 10). Layers are excerpted from each author's maps; however, some symbols have been resized for readability.

Fig. 5 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: Type A (nominative-accusative)

Fig. 6 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: Type B (ergative-absolutive)

Fig. 7 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: Type C (active-inactive or split intransitive)

Fig. 8 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: Type D (tripartite)

Fig. 9 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: Type E (neutral or hierarchical)

Fig. 10 Alignment patterns in Asia and Africa: Types F (complex split) and G (other)

3. Discussion

The maps presented above show certain substantial geographical distributions, suggesting the history of the diffusion of linguistic patterns. Herein, we examine the distributions of each alignment pattern.

Herein, Type A refers to morphological and syntactic nominative-accusative patterns, distinguishing P from A and S. All language groups, except the Chukotko-Kamchatkan, Ainu, Austronesian, and Caucasian languages, involve lects with nominative-accusative patterns. Therefore, its distribution is much broader than that of other types, covering Asia and Africa.

Type A4 (neutral marking but syntactically nominative-accusative, marked by the symbol —) has distribution in peripheral regions of Afro-Eurasia, that is, East and Southeast Asia and West and South Africa, as noted in Shirai (2023). This map provides some additional insights. Type A1 (marked with !) is concentrated in the eastern regions, suggesting an areal tendency. Languages that have nominative-accusative verbal person marking (A2, marked with < , and A3, with \>) are far more widely distributed than those that do not have it (A1 and A4).

The ergative-absolutive pattern plotted in Fig. 6 presents a continuous distribution (Shirai 2023), except for Chukotko-Kamchatkan (Northeast Asia) and part of the Nilo-Saharan languages (Central Africa). Moreover, ergative-absolutive-type verbal person marking (Types B2 and B3, marked with \nabla and \nabla , respectively) is found across the western half of the distribution, except the Chukotko-Kamchatkan languages.

Notably, Suzuki (2021: 58), in an earlier publication of our project, mentioned that Tibetic languages (Tibeto-Burman), Domaaki (Indo-Aryan), and Hunza Burushaski (a language isolate in South Asia) feature a common source for their word forms denoting ‘rice’, although no intense language contact has been reported between these languages. They are all located in a continuous geographical area in which the ergative-absolutive pattern is found in Fig. 6. These facts suggest an early interaction among peoples in the area that diffused the ergative-absolutive type.

As shown in Fig. 7, the split intransitive pattern is absent from Africa and very rare in Asia: one Indo-Aryan language, one Austronesian language, and various dialects of Japanese and Ryukyuan feature this pattern. Due to the few attested lects, discussing their geographical distribution across language groups is difficult.

The tripartite pattern in Asia overlaps with the ergative-absolutive pattern; however, it shows a narrow geographical distribution. As indicated in Fig. 8, languages in continuous regions of western India and the Himalayas’ western, southern, and eastern foothills feature the tripartite pattern. Moreover, in South Asia, most languages with the tripartite pattern also have the ergative-absolutive pattern as a split (Yoshioka 2023;

see also Fig. 2). These distributions suggest that, in this area, the tripartite pattern is newer than the ergative-absolutive pattern. Further, it is also found in Southwestern Japanese dialects, one Nilo-Saharan language, and one Austronesian language.

Fig. 9 presents the distribution of patterns with no case marking or syntactic distinction with respect to whether A or P is treated in the same way as S. This pattern is mainly found in Northeast Asia, Inland China, and South Asia. One Nilo-Saharan language also has this pattern, with a split in the nominative-accusative case marking.

Finally, Fig. 10 presents the distribution of languages with a complex split (Type F) or patterns other than A–E (Type G). We find two substantial patterns in “Other types” (Type G): transitive and symmetrical patterns. The transitive pattern (indicated by the symbols , also features a split in this pattern) shows a regional distribution around the borders of Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Iran, in addition to Northwest Iran. These languages belong to the Indo-Aryan, Nuristani, and Iranian language groups of the Indo-European family. The distribution overlaps with, but is narrower than, the ergative-absolutive pattern. This distribution indicates that the transitive is also newer than the ergative-absolutive pattern, as Iwasaki (2023: 121) noted. The symmetrical pattern is represented by many Austronesian languages (Utsumi 2023). In addition to these patterns, some Nilo-Saharan languages show a bidirectional pattern (Nakao 2023: 129).

4. Conclusion

This study developed linguistic maps to illustrate alignment patterns in Asia and Africa in relation to the contrast between intransitive and highly transitive constructions and the geolinguistic analysis of the maps. The alignment patterns are motivated by a distinction between grammatical relations and are limited in terms of their options; therefore, the same type may coincidentally occur at different points. However, this study also confirmed the existence of areal tendencies that reflect past diffusion of linguistic patterns. The geographical distributions of the ergative-absolutive, tripartite, and transitive patterns suggest their histories: ergative-absolutive patterns exhibit a continuous distribution around the Himalayas, South Asia, and West Asia, whereas the tripartite and transitive patterns are distributed in small but overlapping regions to the ergative-absolutive. The distribution of the ergative-absolutive partially overlaps with the distribution of a word form found earlier in our project. These facts suggest that the ergative-absolutive type diffused through past interactions, and the tripartite and transitive types arose in the ergative-absolutive patterns. The nominative-accusative patterns that do not show verbal person marking also show an areal tendency.

Notably, this study was not conducted to capture the general characteristics of each language but to focus on the restricted constructions, as mentioned in Section 1, because it is based on the geolinguistic method. Different distributions will be found under different conditions; therefore, investigating constructions under various conditions is necessary to thoroughly understand this issue. Comparing the maps of different features enables us to find more substantial distributions of linguistic features that can be used to tell people's history.

Notes for copyright

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